

Embryogenic and nonembryogenic callus induction and plant regeneration from indica rice genotypes.

Genotype	Callus type ^a	Callus growth ^b	Calli plated for regeneration (no.)	Plants regenerated ^c (no.)	
				Green	Albino
Chambal	E	+++ (50)	40	219	181
CH1039	E	+++ (50)	48	588	-
CH988	NE	++ (25)	-	-	-
HPU5039-P1p13-4-4-6-3B	E	+ (12)	48	72	-
HPU2216	NE	++ (37)	-	-	-
HPU5101	E	++ (17)	52	130	-
HPU2202	E	+++ (58)	32	72	-
Himalaya 1	NR	-	-	-	-
Himalaya 741	NE	+ (25)	-	-	-
Himdhan	E	+++ (42)	44	297	-
IR18482-P1p3-2-5-2	E	++ (8)	32	-	-
IR36	NE	+ (25)	-	-	-
K39	NE	+ (37)	-	-	-
Kaladhan	NE	+++ (75)	-	-	-
R575	NE	++ (8)	-	-	-

^aCallus induction medium = MS + 2.5 mg 2,4-D/liter. E = embryogenic callus, NE = nonembryogenic callus, NR = no response. ^b+ = poor, ++ = moderate, +++ = good to excellent, - = not attempted. Values in parentheses indicate the percentage of response among replicates. ^cPlant regeneration medium = MS + 1.0 mg BAP/liter and 0.1 mg NAA/liter.

(see table). HPU5039-P1p13-4-4-6-3B, HPU2202, and HPU5101 regenerated into green plantlets but at a lower frequency. IR18482-P1p3-2-5-2 did not regenerate. Chambal, CH1039, and Himdhan were considered more responsive than the others to callus formation and plant regeneration. Chambal had a high frequency of albino plants.

The results indicate that embryogenic callus formation and plant regeneration ability vary among indica rice genotypes. ■

Effect of interaction between genotype and culture medium on callus induction and plant regeneration of anther culture of Vietnamese indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

M. Don Nguyen, Food Crops Research Institute, Hai Hung, Vietnam; and F. J. Zapata, IRRRI

We evaluated the response of 12 Vietnamese indica rice genotypes (including F₁ promising lines, and varieties) to anther culture using several callus induction media (CIM) and plant regeneration media (PRM). Anther culture can complement the rice breeding program in Vietnam by offering the advantage of rapid achievement of homozygosity.

Anthers with microspores at the mid-uninucleate to early binucleate stage of development were plated on CIM G1, Fj, and L8 (Table 1) at a density of 15 anthers/ml of medium. The plated anthers were incubated in the dark at 25±1°C. Callus induction percentage was recorded 2 mo after culture and calculated as number of callus-producing anthers relative to total anthers plated. We transferred calli of 1-2 mm diameter to

Table 1. Constituents of callus induction media.

Constituent	Medium (mg/liter)		
	G1	Fj	L8
KNO ₃	2830	3150	3000
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	463	220	-
KH ₂ PO ₄	170	540	540
MgSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	185	185	185
CaCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O	440	150	150
MnSO ₄ · 4H ₂ O	4.4	22.3	22.3
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.5	10.0	10.0
H ₃ BO ₃	6.2	6.0	6.0
KI	0.83	1.0	1.0
CuSO ₄ · 5H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025
CoCl ₂ · 6H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025
NaMoO ₄ · 2H ₂ O	0.025	0.025	0.025
Na ₂ EDTA	37.25	37.25	37.25
FeSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	27.85	27.85	27.85
Glycine	2.0	2.0	-
Thiamine-HCl	2.5	2.0	2.5
Pyridoxine-HCl	2.5	2.0	5.0
Nicotinic acid	2.5	2.0	3.0
Lactalbumin	-	-	500.0
Casein hydrolysate	500.00	500.0	-
Inositol	100.0	100.0	100.0
2,4-D	2.0	0.5	0.5
Naphthalene acetic acid	2.5	2.5	2.0
Sucrose	40000	40000	40000
Agar	8000	8000	8000
pH	5.8	5.8	5.8

11 PRM for plant regeneration, which was calculated as number of calli producing green plants relative to total calli plated.

Genotype and medium interaction showed significant effect on callus induction (Table 2). All genotypes responded with callus induction being genotype- and medium-dependent. Callus induction ranged from 1.8% in IR64/IR2588-1-3-2 on G1 medium to 27.9% in Nep Hoa Vang on L8 medium. Among the three CIM tested, L8 gave the highest average callus induction of 19.5%, followed by G1 and Fj.

Green plant production ranged from 13.3% in IR64/IR2588-1-3-2 to 25.4% in IR8/828//Nep Ga Gay (Table 2). Significant effects of the interactions among genotypes, CIM, and PRM were observed. Among the PRM used, however, M6 medium (Murashige and

Table 2. Interaction between genotype and medium on callus induction and plant regeneration of Indica rices.

Genotype	Callus induction ^a (%)			Green plant regeneration ^b (%)	
	Fj	G1	L8		
C15/Nep Hoa Vang (F ₁)	4.8	efghijk	13.0 cd	15.6 c	17.7 cd
C15/Nep Ga Gay (F ₁)	5.5	defghi	15.2 bc	15.4 c	15.1 de
IR1529-680-3-2/Pelita (line)	7.0	cde	19.4 ab	25.4 ab	13.3 f
IR8/DU//IR529 (line)	4.9	efghijk	16.8 abc	22.5 b	17.9 cd
IR8/828//Nep Ga Gay (line)	3.8	hijklmn	5.6 f	17.1 c	25.4 a
IR8/DU//C4-63///IR1569 (line)	5.2	defghi	18.9 ab	22.1 b	18.0 c
184/IR8 (line)	3.7	hijklmn	6.8 ef	11.4 d	21.7 b
IR64/IR2588-1-3-2 (line)	2.7	mno	1.8 g	16.4 c	13.3 f
C10 (variety)	5.7	cdefgh	16.7 abc	11.2 d	16.3 cd
Xuan So 4 (variety)	13.2 a		19.5 a	24.1 ab	23.0 ab
Nep Hoa Vang (variety)	7.8 bc		18.7 ab	27.9 a	14.9 ef
Nep Ga Gay (variety)	4.6	fghijkl	13.3 cd	24.6 ab	17.5 cd

^aMeans in a column with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Means among CIM in a row are separated using LSD_{0.05} = 2.59. ^bThe response for each variety is the mean of 11 PRM.

Skoog basal supplemented with 1.0 mg naphthalene acetic acid/liter and 8 mg kinetin/liter) produced the most green

plants. A total of 3211 green plants were regenerated from these materials; 40% of the regenerants produced seeds. ■

Yield potential

Different grades of grain occur during grain filling in short- and medium-duration rice

N. M. Chau and S. C. Bhargava, Plant Physiology Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India

We graded grain during grain filling in five rice cultivars in 1991 kharif (monsoon) season at IARI. Panicles emerging synchronously from the main tillers were labeled. Five panicles per cultivar were collected at a 5-d interval from 15 to 35 d after panicle emergence (DAPE). Panicles were threshed and graded by specific gravity method.

Good and high density grains (HDG) constituted 67% of total grains in Rasi at 15 DAPE (see table). This percentage increased towards maturity, although at 25 DAPE it nearly stabilized at 77% of the total grains/panicle. Unfilled grains constituted 16% of the total as early as 15 DAPE and declined gradually towards maturity.

In Pusa 2-21, HDG made up about 55% of the total grains at 15 DAPE; this percentage remained almost stable until maturity.

Pusa 743 has good grain type. The occurrence of good grains/panicle was almost stable around 20 DAPE, although at 15 DAPE, good grade grains were only 8.8% of the total. HDG/panicle was 9.2% at 20 DAPE, dropped, and then climbed to 10% at 35 DAPE.

In Pusa 169, unfilled grains coupled with poor and average grain accounted for 90% of total grains at 15 DAPE, but dropped to 71% at maturity.

Good plus HDG grains made up 46% of total grains/panicle at 15 DAPE in Jaya and 65% at 30 DAPE. The appearance of this high percentage of good plus HDG at 15 DAPE indicates that this is a genotypic character distinct from large grain size and high total grains/panicle.

Many HDG appeared as early as 15 DAPE in short-duration cultivars such as Rasi and Pusa 2-21. HDG was barely evident up to 30 DAPE in medium-duration cultivars, such as Pusa 169 and Pusa 743. These results suggest that grain filling may be a predetermined phenomenon or a genotypic character. ■

Number and percentage of different grades of grain/panicle at successive growth stages during grain filling. IARI, New Delhi, India, 1991 kharif.

Cultivar	DAPE ^a	High density grains/panicle		Good grains/panicle		Av grains/panicle		Poor grains/panicle		Unfilled grains/panicle		Total grains/panicle (no.)
		no.	% ^b	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	
Rasi	15	80	(58.4)	12	(8.8)	8	(5.8)	16	(11.4)	21	(15.6)	137
	20	96	(62.3)	12	(7.8)	8	(5.2)	16	(10.4)	22	(14.3)	154
	25	91	(64.5)	18	(12.8)	7	(5.0)	8	(5.7)	17	(12.0)	141
	30	59	(48.8)	43	(35.5)	4	(3.3)	4	(3.3)	11	(9.1)	121
	35	104	(61.9)	31	(18.5)	7	(4.2)	11	(6.5)	15	(8.9)	168

continued on next page